

The Attitude *in Vitro* of 10 Ubiquitous Bacteria in Seawater Polluted By Benzene and Toluene

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Abstract

This study focuses on specifying a number of ubiquitous non-fastidious bacteria isolated from urine hospitalized patients for their abilities to degrade benzene and toluene. Using the MALDI-Tof technique (Bruker Daltonics), these opportunist bacteria have been identified. The bacteria were inoculated and incubated in sterile water contaminated with pure benzene and toluene for 63 days, at room temperature with continuous oxygenation. Analysis by Gas Chromatography/ Mass Spectrometry (GC / MS) HP6890 / HP 5973 MS (Agilent Technologies) allowed us to determine the concentration of each hydrocarbon and their derivatives. The results showed that not only the strains were able to completely degrade benzene and toluene in a single derivative: cyclohexane after less than 30 days. But even reveals variations in cyclohexane concentrations from one strain to another. Results reveal also that the Consumption of toluene by our strains was easier than with benzene, up to complete removal of toluene derivative in both species S1687 and S1671. The 2 strains belonging to the family Moraxellaceae S1670 and S1671 degrade benzene faster with concentrations 0.0475 µg/µl and 0.0727 µg/µl respectively, While both strains S5 and S476 of the Enterobacteriaceae family, had consumed totally and more easily cyclohexane (benzene derivative) with the lowest concentrations 0.0316 µg/µl and 0.0449 µg/µl respectively, this research confirmed that benzene, toluene and their derivatives were completely consumed without producing other identifiable intermediate metabolites.

Key words: Aromatic hydrocarbons, Benzene, Toluene, GC / MS HP6890 / HP 5973 MS (Agilent Technologies), MALDI-Tof (Bruker Daltonics), Ubiquitous bacteria.

Introduction

The environment, health and economy are three distinct words but closely related. Despite the fact of the connection between them, the environment is the link that connects all the natural conditions that can affect living organisms. Given the human increase since 1990s, social and environmental tensions threaten human health and the balance of both marine and terrestrial ecosystems (MBONIGABA et al., 2009).

Human activity (industrial, agriculture, fishing, tourism, etc.) is one of the major environmental aggressions. According to the commitments from the Blue Book of the Oceans Round Table (MEEDDM., 2009), 80% of the pollution comes from land-based activities (urban, agricultural and industrial discharges) and 20% from maritime activities. However, the most conventional the oldest and the most mediatized of marine pollution remains indisputably hydrocarbon pollution (MONTEIL, 2009).

Whatever their sources public or private, regional or global, numerous reports regularly testify of the continuing deterioration of the state of the environment causing irreversible risks (Sandrine, 2002), such as those 50 years of silent pollution in the Niger Delta, the amount of oil that escapes every year

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from terminals, pipelines and pumping stations exceed our predictions, forests and farmland were covered of a shiny layer of oily liquid, the wells of drinking water were polluted (Samata, 2016). Over the economic and ecological damage, the impact on human health is considerable, even mortal. The most illustrative example is the explosion of the DeepWater Horizon oil rig on April 20, 2010 by killing 11 people generating a fire, and then a large-scale oil spill, the ecological disaster is unprecedented in the United States, 780 million liters of oil spilled in the Gulf of Mexico from the Atlantic Ocean (Geraud et al., 2010).

Hydrocarbons whether total or aromatic, monocyclic or polycyclic, contain a very large number of organic compounds. The most toxic are Aromatic Hydrocarbons, as they are classified as carcinogenic, mutagenic and reprotoxic. In addition to their ubiquitous nature, their high toxicity justifies their classification as Persistent Organic Pollutants (POP) and their inclusion as priority substances on the lists of the European Commission, the United States Environmental Protection Agency and the World Health Organization (Marchand *et al.*, 1996, Khodaei K *et al.*, 2017).

Various solutions have been proposed for treating media contaminated with mono / polycyclic hydrocarbons, including physico-chemical processes such as stripping, flotation, thermal desorption, solvent extraction, ultrasound, electrochemical treatment (FRITSCHÉ and HOFRICHTER .2008). These methods have proved very expensive, because they must also be rigorously tested in order to determine the amount of reagent to be used, and prevent them from being in default or in excess. It is important to know the properties of the environment to avoid the risk of side reactions that would lead to the formation of new pollutants, which is difficult to dominate in aquatic environments.

Currently, research is moving towards the elimination of aromatic hydrocarbons by bioprocesses. The interest of these new techniques mainly resides in their non-polluting aspect, and the absence of chemical by-products (LAN 2009). Hydrocarbon-degrading bacteria are not a new invention, they have been around for millions of years. They are ubiquitous in seawater worldwide, but only in small quantities and feed on traces of naturally occurring hydrocarbons in the environment. The new challenge for these bacteria today is to look at all the anthropogenic point pollution to degrade huge volumes of aromatic hydrocarbons on a given site. Despite their ecological potential importance, few knowledge about the biological processes of these bacteria.

We are interested in the biodegradation of monoaromatic hydrocarbons such as benzene, toluene, because they are considered as the most common mono-aromatic pollutants, except that, benzene is the most robust in almost all field studies, as a carcinogen and therefore the most toxic (Grbic-Gralic and Vogel., 1987). It is in this context that we have studied the biodegradation of benzene and toluene by pure bacterial strains that can degrade aromatic hydrocarbons and evaluate this degradation while quantifying the growth of our strains, and this, for large scale exploitation.

The main objective of this project was to explore the diversity of bacteria capable of degrading aromatic hydrocarbons in an aquatic environment polluted chronically by hydrocarbons (junction of 3 points of industrial discharges). Our approach has clearly distinguished itself from classical approaches based on the isolation of pure strains on selective media, the limits of which are known since less than 5% of the bacterial species are cultivable.

Our study allowed us to identify and target aerobic-facultative bacteria that are both easy to cultivate and persistent, capable of degrading high concentrations of aromatic hydrocarbons (benzene and toluene) under adverse conditions. . To this end, an experimental approach was developed, consisting in isolating 10 bacterial strains and injecting them into sterile sea water contaminated with toluene and benzene separately, then comparing the evolution and the behavior of each bacteria in relation with the pollutant.

Materials and methods

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I- Description of the Refining Complex (RA1 / K) of Skikda- Algeria:

Originally, Skikda refinery was managed by the national company Sonatrach in 1982, after in 1988 the petroleum refining and distribution companies were separated and erected into national oil refining and distribution companies (ERDP- NAFTAL).

In 1988, the refining was separated from the distribution business is erected in national oil refining company (NAFTEC), since April 18, 1998 it became a subsidiary which shares are 100% owned by Sonatrach with a registered capital of 12 billion dinars, named National Oil Refining Company (NAFTEC spa). The start of construction of the Skikda refinery took place on 02/01/1976 by the manufacturer: SNAMPROGETTI (Italy). Skikda refinery (RA1K) is located in the industrial area 7 km east of the city on an area of 190ha.

1. Treatment of effluents rejected:

Wastewater is water that has been used to be treated before being reintroduced to other sources of water so that it does not cause pollution from these other sources. Wastewater comes from several sources. All that we evacuate by flushing and when using your sinks is considered waste water. Rainwater, as well as the various pollutants that flow into sewers, end up in sewage treatment plants. Wastewater can also come from agricultural and industrial sources. Some wastewater is harder to treat than others, for example; Industrial wastewater can be difficult to treat, while domestic wastewater is relatively easy to treat. (However, it is becoming more and more difficult to treat domestic waste due to the increasing number of pharmaceuticals and personal care products that are increasingly present in domestic wastewater.

The treatment of industrial wastewater is a secondary operation of course, but one in which the maximum of care must be taken. Therefore, we must draw attention to the problems posed by industrial discharges that can pollute the environment very seriously.

To do this, we must present the different types of treatments that can be used depending on the nature and composition of the water, highlighting the performance of each and the conditions to be met for the best results.

To purify the water, it is generally necessary to combine several elementary treatments which bases can be: physical, chemical, and biological, and the effect of which is to eliminate firstly the suspended matter, subsequently the colloidal substances, then the dissolved substances (mineral or organic), and finally it is necessary to correct some characteristics.

To allow a fairly clear description of the process, the RA1K drain collection system based on the separation and treatment of polluted water is determined.

- Wash water from boiler air heaters.
- Draining filters after regeneration.
- Drainage for cleaning tanks containing hydrocarbons.
- Drainage of accumulated water.
- Water drainage (treatment and cooling) of the process units.

Description

The polluted water reaches the ETP-2-1101 treatment unit by means of a network of pipes discharging the hydraulic load into the collection basin.

Two pumping stations are installed at basin:

- The first includes pumps designed to transfer water in excess of the nominal flow to a specific tank for settling.
- The second also includes pumps that allowed the transfer of nominal flow to the preliminary treatment.

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The treatment of waters with high hydrocarbon pollution is carried out in two separators, which are arranged in parallel or in basin's flotation of the oil particles and the sedimentation of suspended solids. Each basin is equipped with an "API" bridge carriage, a bottom scraper and a surface skimmer (Fig.1).

Figure 01: Photograph showing the basin responsible for the treatment of heavily polluted water by hydrocarbons - (ETP-2) of the Skikda refinery.

The bottom scraper collects the sludge from which it is sent to a sludge mixing basin. While the surface skimmer carries the oils and foam to another basin.

- Mixing Waters and Flocculants:

The water which has undergone the first treatment in the two separators arrives at the mixing basin, in which the iron sulphate (FeSO_4) is introduced to cause the flocculation (Fig.2). The intense stirring ($500\text{w} / \text{m}^3$) makes it possible to obtain a perfect mixture of these currents which flow subsequently to the control basin of the pH.

Figure 02: Photograph showing the first iron sulphate (FeSO_4) (ETP-2) treatment at the Skikda refinery.

pH control is necessary to maintain optimal values during flocculation using the HCl or $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ assay. The stirring is obtained by blowing $15\text{ m}^3 / \text{h} / \text{m}^2$ of the vessel also with the aim of oxidizing the iron from the divalent state to the trivalent state which involves the total precipitation of iron such as $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$.

- Flocculation

By union of polyelectrolytes and the slight mechanical stirring $75\text{w} / \text{m}^3$ is carried out the coalescence of the flakes which are formed in the tank, so it was noticed that the emulsified oils in very fine droplets are adsorbed on the flakes.

- Dissolved Air Flotation

Currents water recovered, are intimately mixed at the basin's inlet with circular plan. By relaunching the dissolved air in form of bubbles having a diameter of $10 - 30\ \mu\text{m}$. To obtain the flotation of the

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suspended materials contained in the water (Fig. 3).

Figure 3: Photograph showing the flocculation basin - effluent treatment plant (ETP2) of the Skikda refinery.

A system of surface skimmers transports what is floated to the funnel, from where it is transferred in continuity by gravity to another basin, a bottom scraper transports what is sedimented.

- pH correction, flocculant addition, nutrient dosing

In principle, the optimum pH of flocculation coincides with which is required at the entry of the biological phase, between [7-7.5]. For this purpose, a basin has been designed for the ratio of the pH to the values required for the biological treatment by the determination of HCl or $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, moreover it carries out an assay of flocculant FeSO_4 and polyelectrolyte to improve if it is necessary for sedimentation of active sludge.

- Activated sludge biological treatment

The current from the pH correction tank arrives at the active sludge basins which are equipped with aeration turbines (Fig.4), deliver the necessary oxygen to the process. The volume of the aeration basins is 1160m^3 and the expected concentration of sludge is $3.5\text{g} / \text{m}^3$. The turbines have a total oxygen capacity of $50\text{ kg} / \text{h}$.

Figure 4: Photograph showing the biological pond of the effluent treatment plant (ETP-2) of the Skikda refinery.

The excess sludge, drawn by the current, is sent continuously to the pond, which corresponds to a concentration of $2\text{ m}^3 / \text{h}$ to be extracted in continuity (Fig.5).

Figure 5: Photograph showing the excess sludge disposal system (ETP2) Skikda refinery.

- Filtering on Sand:

The pump relaunches the stream from the biological treatment and accumulates in a pond. In the three sand filters, the separation of suspended solids that are not sedimented in the decanter as well as that of the oil particles (Fig.6) will take place.

Figure 6: Photograph showing the three sand filters - (ETP-2) - Skikda refinery.

The filters are dimensioned so as to allow digestion of the maximum flow rate in 2 groups when the third is in the backwash phase. This is done automatically at least once a day. Since it can also be done manually. The backwash air is supplied by a blower and the water is sorted from the pool and fed by a pump.

- Activated carbon filtration:

The water from the sand filters undergoes the charcoal filtration in the 4 groups. Counter wash carbon filters are done manually.

The maximum backwash interval shouldn't be greater than 72 hours (03 days) in order to avoid packaging of activated carbon. The air and the backwash water come from the same machines designed for sand filters. The effluent, collected by the equipment zone, flows into a specific basin.

The backwash has the function of eliminating the packaging of coal and suspended solids from sand filters in case of malfunction of the latter. The renewal of the activated carbon charge is carried out in pairs of filters (5 - 10 years).

- Oil treatment Oils separated in the accumulation tank (Fig.7) where the oils flow to the sump. The pump refers them to the treatment of oils as slop at unit 600.

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Figure 7: Photograph showing the oil accumulation tank of the effluent treatment plant (ETP-2) of the Skikda refinery.

- Biological treatment

The elimination of organic matter involves the use of biological treatments that engage living organisms, mainly bacteria.

These biological processes, most often aerobic, rely on the biodegradation of organic materials in the presence of oxygen by heterotrophic microorganisms. They reproduce the natural self-purification phenomena that occur in the natural environment.

Fixed culture processes where the biomass purifier is fixed on the supports. The water to be treated flows in contact with these supports. Microorganisms therefore fix organic pollution and degrade it (biofiltration, for example).

Free culture processes where biomass is suspended in the water to be treated. The microorganisms fix the pollution and develop in the form of biological flocs that can be separated from the water treated by decantation (activated sludge for example).

II- Description of the Sampling sites

In order to maintain the hostile conditions of seawater polluted by industrial discharges, and not to be restricted to refinery releases, water samples were taken from the junction of three discharges sites: -a Effluent Treatment Station 1100 (Effluent Treatment Plant 2) Skikda -b- Oued Zeramna refinery -c- Oued Saf-saf, Skikda industrial area (Fig.8) (Table1).

Fig. 8. Location of study and sampling sites (Google map2015)

a- [ETP2 1101 : 36°52'00.4"N 6°57'57.7"E , b- [Oued zeramna 36°52'41.2"N 6°56'08.9"E],
c- [Oued safsaf 36°87'23.4"N 6°94'25.7"E].

Faced with the difficulties of obtaining and cultivating naturally occurring bacteria in aquatic and even telluric environments contaminated by aromatic hydrocarbons, we used ubiquitous species isolated from human samples, which have the power to degrade the aromatic hydrocarbons (Morlett-Chavez et al.2010; Tarayre. 2012).

Table 1. Geographical coordinates of the discharge sites of the industrial zone, Wilaya of Skikda-Algeria.

Site's name	Geographical location
a-Effluent Treatment Plant 2 (ETP2 1101)	36°52'00.4"N 6°57'57.7"E
b-Zeramna ouad	36°52'41.2"N 6°56'08.9"E
c-Saf-saf ouad	°87'23.4"N 6°94'25.7"E

III- Microbiology Techniques:

Microorganisms such as bacteria, fungi and microalgae play a key role in the removal of monoaromatic hydrocarbons in situ. Since bacteria are faster and easier to handle (Table 2), the use of these bacteria is preferred (Roger and Jacq 2000, Prenafeta-Boldu et al 2002, Schulze and Tiehm 2004, Nikolova and Nenov 2005).

Table 2. Some microorganisms involved in the degradation of monoaromatic hydrocarbons (Be: Benzene, To: Toluene, Eb: Ethylbenzene, Xy: Xylenes, oXy: o-xylene, pXy: p-xylene, mXy: m-xylene).

Bacteria	Hydrocarbons used	References
<i>Rhodococcus rhodochrous</i>	Be, To, Eb, Xy	Deeb and Alvarez-Cohen (1999)
<i>Rhodococcus sp. RRI, RR2</i>	Be, To, Eb, mXy, pXy	Deeb and Alvarez-Cohen (2000)
<i>Ralstonia pickettii PKO1</i>	To	Parales et al.,(2000)
<i>Rhodococcus sp. strain DK17</i>	Be, To, Eb, oXy	Farhadian and al. 2007
<i>Pseudomonas sp. ATCC 55595</i>	Be, pXy	Collins and Daugulis (1999)
<i>Burkholderia cepacia G4</i>	To	Parales and al. (2000)
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Be	Kim and al. (2003)
<i>Pseudomonas fluorescens</i>	Be, To, Eb, oXy	Shim and al. (2002,2005)
<i>Pseudomonas putida F1</i>	Be, To, Eb	Parales and al. (2000)
<i>Pseudomonas putida souche mt- 2</i>	To, mXy, pXy	Morasch and al. (2002)
<i>Achromobacter xylosoxidans</i>	Be, To, Eb, Xy	Nielsen and al. (2006)
Blastochloris sulfovirdis ToP1	To	Van Hamme and al. (2003)
Desulfobacterium cetonicum	To	Shim and al. (2002,2005)

Bacterial strains used

Given the difficulties to cultivate bacteria found naturally in aquatic and telluric environments contaminated by aromatic hydrocarbons, we have used ubiquitous species isolated from human pathological samples (Urine) having specificity to degrade aromatic hydrocarbons. The use of bacteria isolated from human samples for purely environmental purposes is attempted for the first time (Morlett-Chavez et al.2010; Tarayre. 2012)..

Based on bibliographic data, their common properties as well as the fact that they belong to the same genus in varieties of different environments, we selected about 10 Nos bacteria which were isolated from different urine specimens at the laboratory of the Military University Regional Hospital of Constantine-Algeria (Table 3). Whose 6 belongs to the *Enterobacteriaceae* family, 2 to the *Moraxellaceae* family, 1 to the *Pseudomonadaceae* family and one to the *Enterococaceae*.

Table 3. The bacteria used in the trial.

Reference	Species
S05	<i>Citrobacter freundii</i>
S476	<i>Citrobacter youngae</i>
S1620	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>

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S1664	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>
S02	<i>Klebsiella oxytoca</i>
S1687	<i>Serratia marcescens</i>
S1670	<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>
S1671	<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>
S1850	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>
S1663	<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>

The isolated bacterial species were identified by the Api[®]20 E galleries. Confirmation was made by Maldi-Tof mass spectrometry (Bruker, biotyper 2.0).

Proteomic biochemical characteristics

III-2- Caractères biochimiques protéomiques a- Famille des *Enterobacteriaceae*.

Commonly called enterobacteria or enteric bacteria. They are composed of bacilli and include many bacterial genus of which the most commonly isolated are: *Escherichia*, *Salmonella*, *Shigella*, *Klebsiella*, *Proteus*, *Enterobacter*, *Citrobacter*, *Serratia*.

Enterobacteriaceae are straight bacilli, aerobic-anaerobic optional, negative oxidize, reducing nitrates to nitrite, fermenting glucose with or without gas production, immobile (*Klebsiella*, *Shigella*, *Yersinia pestis*), easily cultivable on usual media.

Many species of *Enterobacteriaceae* are commonly distributed, and usually without any damage, in humans and animals. Species also occur in different types of terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems. But among the 130 species currently listed, some are pathogenic for humans: various strains for example: *E. coli*, *Yersinia pestis*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Shigella dysenteriae*...(Bousseboua.2005)

b- Family of *Moraxellaceae*

The family *Moraxellaceae* is a member of the order *Pseudomonadales*, currently countaning the genus *Acinetobacter*, *Moraxella* and *Psychrobacter*. Many of these microorganisms are part of this family have questionable identities, generating difficulties in the interpretation of publications (Shuai Li *et al.*, 2017). *Acinetobacter* are ubiquitous bacteria and are part of the normal flora of humans and animals (Avril JL *et al.*, 1992).

c- Family of *Pseudomonadaceae*

This family currently includes 04 genus: *Pseudomonas* and *Xanthomonas*, most of them are phyto-pathogenic, they are also found in the context of hospital-acquired infections. And *Frateuria* and *Zoogloea* exclusively saprophyte (Avril JL *et al.*, 1992).

d- Family of *Enterococcaceae*

They are commensals of gastrointestinal flora, there are about thirty species: *Enterococcus faecalis* and *Enterococcus faecium* are the most frequently isolated in pathological situation (Avril JL *et al.*, 1992).

MALDI-TOF: Matrix Assisted Laser Desorption/Ionization-Time Of Flight

MALDI-Tof is a technique that was introduced as an ionization method for a wide range of biological molecules in 1998 by Hillenkamp and Karas and has since become a generalized analytical tool for analyzing proteins (Hillenkamp and Karas, 1991).

The sample (young culture) to be analyzed by MALDI-TOF is prepared by mixing the sample with an excess solution of an organic absorbent compound called a matrix. When the matrix crystallizes during drying, the sample trapped in the co-crystallized matrix also is bombarded with a laser beam.

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Desorption and ionization with the laser beam generates mono-proton ions from analytes in the sample (Fig.9). The protonated ions are then accelerated to a fixed potential and the latter are separated from each other on the basis of the mass / charge ratio (m/z). The loaded analytes are then detected and measured using time-of-flight (TOF) analyzers (Neelja *et al.*, 2015).

During the MALDI-TOF analysis, the m/z ratio of an ion is measured by determining the time it takes to travel the length of the flight tube (Yates, 1998) and to produce a mass spectrum. The resulting mass spectrum is a kind of unique and specific fingerprint of the analyzed microorganism protein composition (Protein Microorganism Fingerprint), which can be compared to a spectral database (Descy *et al.*, 2010).

Fig. 9. Diagram showing the principle of MALDI-TOF MS.

The identification of bacteria by MALDI-TOF MS is made by comparing the MS spectrum (PMF) of an unknown microbial isolates in comparison to the MS spectrum of the known microbial isolates contained in the database. For the identification of germs at the species level, a typical mass range of m/z of 2-20 kDa is used, which mainly represents ribosomal proteins with some maintenance proteins. Ribosomal proteins are the most abundant, accounting for about 60-70% of the dry weight of a microbial cell. The mass range of 2 -20 kDa is used to identify a particular microorganism by associating its PMF with the PMF of the ribosomal proteins contained in a large open database (Drancourt M *et al.*,2010) Thus, the identity of a microorganism can be established by gender and in many cases by species (Fagerquist *et al.*, 2010).

Implementation of experiments on the biodegradation of benzene in seawater In Vitro Preliminary tests

The seawater samples taken were sterilized and then divided into 21 sterile vials, one of which represents the negative test (T0). Each vial contains 1000 ml of sterilized seawater by the autoclaving method, to which pure benzene and pure toluene have been added (purity as shown in Table 04). The flasks were shaken well to obtain a representative sample, thus the initial concentration of benzene and toluene was 250 mg / l. Each vial was subsequently inoculated with a bacterial strain from our list (Table 03) at the rate of about 8×10^{10} bacteria / vial.

Table 4. Characteristics of added Benzene in our samples.

Parameter product	Tank number	Non-aromatic products	Benzene
Benzene	38	0.02 %	99.98 %

At the end of our experiment we obtain 10 bottles containing sea water polluted by benzene, each containing a strain and the same with toluene, while ensuring continuous oxygenation through special engines.

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The inoculated bacteria were cultured on ordinary agar medium and the enrichment was carried out on BHIB broth to facilitate bacterial multiplication (proteose peptone 10.0 g, veal brain's infusion 12.5 g, infusion of heart of beef 5.0 g, glucose 2.0 g, chloride of sodium 5.0g, sodium hydrogenphosphate 2.5g, pH = 7.4).

The flasks were sealed with rubber stoppers to prevent contamination and also to minimize the evaporation of benzene or toluene, and incubated for 63 days at 25 ° C with continuous oxygenation using aquarium engine. Daily cultures were made to monitor the purity of the strains. After 4 weeks the first sample was taken and a second one after 9 weeks to evaluate the biodegradation of benzene and toluene.

Physico-chemical techniques Analysis of benzene by GC /MS

The association of gas chromatography with mass spectrometry is an analytical technique of choice. Due to the high sensitivity of this technique and the quality of the results obtained, it's used to identify many components of complex mixtures such as monocyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (Yassaa *et al.*, 1999). The analysis of benzene and its degradation products was carried out by Gas Chromatography (GC) using an HP6890 (Agilent Technologies) equipped with a column MDN12 (30 mx0.25 mm, 25 µm d stationary phase thickness, Supleco) in which passes ultra-pure helium (Helium purity: 6.0), the vector gas, at 0.5 ml / min. the GC is coupled to an HP 5973 Mass Spectrometry (MS) (Agilent Technologies) mass detector operating with 70eV ionization energy and a 2000 volt voltage. The instrument was set to Total-Ion-Chromatogram (TIC) mode to detect the intensities of all mass spectral peaks belonging to the same scan, including background noise and sample components.

V-1-1 The analysis of benzene and toluene:

To extract the organic material, 1 ml of the negative control and 1 ml of each sample was mixed with 0.5 ml of diethyl ether. The whole is carefully stirred for 15 min to reach the extraction equilibrium, 1 .mu.l of the supernatant was injected into the column with a flow rate of 0.5 ml / min. The temperature of the oven was raised from 45 ° C to 150 ° C at a gradient of 10 ° C / min of pitch, then held for 10 min at 150 ° C. This program has been optimized for the separation of monocyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (Yassaa *et al.*, 1999). The monocyclic aromatic hydrocarbons were indicated between 2 and 17.5 min and detected by the mass spectrometer to be identified. Based on a calibration curve obtained from a standard mixture (provided by Agilent), identification of separated compounds was achieved by retention times in comparison with respective standards and by mass spectra comparison (standards, Wiley and NIST02 library).

Analysis of Cyclohexane by GC / MS

Among the benzene derivatives, cyclohexane. That is obtained by passing a gas stream rich in hydrogen in benzene containing a catalyst of hydrogenation; each molecule of benzene fixes three molecules of hydrogen. Thus cyclohexane is obtained (Table 5). But as regards the conversion of toluene to cyclohexane is still unknown.

Cyclohexane standards were prepared S1, S2, S3, S4, S5, S6 of different concentrations 7.785x10⁻¹, 7.785x10⁻⁴, 7.785x10⁻⁵, 7.785x10⁻⁵, 7.785x10⁻³, 7.785 x10⁻² respectively.

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Table 5. Description and identification of the cyclohexane used.

Product identification	
Product form	Substance
Trade name	Cyclohexane for synthesis
Chemical name	Cyclohexane
Index number	200-661-000
CE number	203-806-2
CAS number	111-82-7
REACH registration number	BA 110-82-7-0109-011
Raw formula	C ₆ H ₁₂
Molar mass	84.16 g/mol

Results

Results of MALDI-OF analysis

For the majority of our bacteria, we were able to identify the species with a credible score (Table 6). The identification by Maldi ToF (Bruker Daltonics) had allowed the confirmation of the results obtained by the Api[®]20 galleries. The two species S1670 and S1664 showed a highly probable identification score: 2.397 and 2.367 respectively. While 7 species which are S1671, S1620, S5, S1663, S1687, S2 and S476 indicate secure genus identification whose score is between [2.277-2.058]. However, strain S1850 has the lowest score of 1.976.

Table 6. The scores of each species identified by MALDI-TOF (or even the meanings of the scores in Table 7 above).

Analyte name	Analyte ID	Organism (best match)	Score value	Organism (second best match)	Score value
A7 (++) (C)	S5	<i>Citrobacter freundii</i>	2.261	<i>Citrobacter freundii</i>	2.199
A8 (++) (B)	S476	<i>Citrobacter youngae</i>	2.058	<i>Citrobacter freundii</i>	2.018
A10 (+++)(A)	S1670	<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	2.367	<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	2.221
D3 (+++)(C)	S1664	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	2.397	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	2.283
D4 (++) (C)	S1620	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	2.270	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	2.226
D5 (++) (A)	S1663	<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	2.158	<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	2.157
D6 (++) (C)	S2	<i>Klebsiell oxytoca</i>	2.151	<i>Raoultella omithinolytica</i>	1.933
D7 (++) (A)	S1671	<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	2.277	<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	2.15
D10 (++) (A)	S1687	<i>Serratia marcescens</i>	2.157	<i>Serratia marcescens</i>	2.022
A9 (+) (B)	S1850	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	1.976	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	1.976

Table 7. Meaning of the scores obtained.

Range	Description	Symbols	Color
2.300...3.000	Highly probable species identification	(+++)	Green
2.000...2.299	Secure genus identification probable species identification	(++)	Green
1.700...1.999	Probable genus identification	(+)	Yellow
0.000...1.699	Not reliable identification	(-)	Red

Results of the Gas Chromatography and Mass Spectrometry (GC / MS) Expression of results before treatment

Analysis of T₀ by GC / MS confirmed the presence of benzene, even before starting the experiment, with a concentration of 0.097 µg / µl (Fig. 10).

Fig. 10. GC/MS spectrum of negative control at T₀: theoretical retention time 2.98 min-
m/z

=78. The signature m/z of the benzene is surrounded in bleu.

-a-Gas Chromatography -b-Mass Spectrometry.

Expression of results after 4 weeks

By analyzing our samples one by one after 4 weeks of incubation, the results obtained indicate the almost complete biotransformation of benzene and toluene to cyclohexane, under normal conditions, by the entirety of the strains, at fluctuating concentrations (Fig. 11).

The highest concentrations of cyclohexane are found in the samples polluted by benzene: 0.0964 µg / µl, 0.0864 µg / µl and 0.0846 µg / µl, are assigned to the bacteria S1663 (*Enterococcus faecalis*), S476 (*Citrobacter youngae*) and S1664 (*Klebsiella pneumoniae*) respectively.

However, after 4 weeks, the lowest concentrations occur in water contaminated with toluene: 0.0154, 0.0183 and 0.0231 in species S1687 (*Serratia marcescens*), S1663 (*Enterococcus faecalis*) and S1671 (*Acinetobacter baumannii*) respectively (see Table 8).

Strains belonging to the family *Enterobacteriaceae* express high concentrations of cyclohexane in water polluted with benzene, which are between [0.0599 and 0.086]. Nevertheless, the species of the family *Moraxellaceae*: S1670 (*Acinetobacter baumannii*) and S1671 (*Acinetobacter baumannii*) have lower concentrations compared to other strains: 0.0727 µg / µl and 0.0475 µg / µl respectively.

While cyclohexane concentrations in toluene polluted waters show clearly low levels in all species. The highest level is 0.0362 µg / µl in strain S1664 (*Klebsiella pneumoniae*) and that in S1687 (*Serratia marcescens*) is the lowest: 0.0154 µg / µl. For the other strains, the concentrations are between [0.0352 µg / µl - 0.0183 µg / µl].

Table 08: Concentrations of cyclohexane after 4 weeks of incubation.

Concentrations	Concentrations of cyclohexane in water polluted with benzene (µg / µl)	Concentrations of cyclohexane in water polluted with toluene (µg / µl)
S 1663	0.0964	0.0183
S 476	0.0864	0.0343
S 1664	0.0846	0.0362
S 1687	0.0835	0.0154
S 1850	0.0821	0.0315
S 02	0.0817	0.0352
S 05	0.0812	0.0344
S 1670	0.0727	0.0277
S 1620	0.0599	0.0276
S 1671	0.0475	0.0231

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Figure 11. Kinetics of Biodegradation of Benzene and Toluene by Culture of Different Bacterial Species After 4 Weeks of Incubation.

(S1850: *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, S05: *Citrobacter freundii*, S476: *Citrobacter youngae*, S02: *Klebsiella oxytoca*, S1687: *Serratia marcescens*, S1664: *Klebsiella pneumonia*, S1671: *Acinetobacter baumannii*, S1663: *Enterococcus faecalis*, S1670: *Acinetobacter baumannii*, S1620: *Klebsiella pneumoniae*).

II-3- Expression of results after 9 weeks:

After 9 weeks of incubation, a decrease in cyclohexane concentrations is observed in media polluted with benzene or with toluene at different proportions (Table 9). But especially in waters contaminated by the latter, go to the total absence of Cyclohexane, this is the case of two strains S1687 (*Serratia marcescens*) and S1971 (*Acinetobacter baumannii*) (Fig.12).

The concentrations of cyclohexane from benzene are between 0.0316 $\mu\text{g} / \mu\text{l}$ in the strain S05 (*Citrobacter freundii*) which consumes it faster than the others, and 0.0824 $\mu\text{g} / \mu\text{l}$ in the strain S1664 (*Klebsiella pneumoniae*) is the slowest with.

While in 9 weeks of incubation the cyclohexane toluene levels are included between 0.0087 $\mu\text{g} / \mu\text{l}$ in the strain S1664 (*Klebsiella pneumoniae*) and 0.0274 $\mu\text{g} / \mu\text{l}$ in the strain S1850 (*Pseudomonas aeruginosa*), underlining the total consumption of cyclohexane in both strains S1687 (*Serratia marcescens*) and (*Acinetobacter baumannii*) (Fig.12).

Table 09: Concentrations of cyclohexane after 9 weeks of incubation.

Concentrations	Concentrations of cyclohexane in water polluted with benzene ($\mu\text{g} / \mu\text{l}$)	Concentrations of cyclohexane in water polluted with toluene ($\mu\text{g} / \mu\text{l}$)
Stains		
S 1663	0.0446	0.0103
S 476	0.0449	0.0208
S 1664	0.0824	0.0087
S 1687	0.0746	No peak
S 1850	0.0632	0.0274
S 02	0.0531	0.0273
S 05	0.0316	0.0192
S 1670	0.0457	0.0207
S 1620	0.0483	0.0167
S 1671	0.0705	No peak

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Figure 12. Kinetics of Biodegradation of Benzene and Toluene by Culture of Different Bacterial Species After 9 Weeks of Incubation.

(S1850: *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, S05: *Citrobacter freundii*, S476: *Citrobacter youngae*, S02: *Klebsiella oxytoca*, S1687: *Serratia marcescens*, S1664: *Klebsiella pneumonia*, S1671: *Acinetobacter baumannii*, S1663: *Enterococcus faecalis*, S1670: *Acinetobacter baumannii*, S1620: *Klebsiella pneumoniae*).

Discussion

Monoaromatic hydrocarbons in particular benzene are compounds mutagenic and reprotoxic. Toluene and benzene are considered the most recalcitrant which makes them very difficult to oxidize both chemically and biologically. These compounds has been shown to serve as carbon and energy sources for aerobic bacteria growing with nitrate, manganese, ferric iron, sulfate, or oxygen as the sole electron acceptor (Chakraborty and Coates, 2004). This has been confirmed by the results of Hunkeler *et al*, the added oxidants were almost completely consumed during the last year of engineered in situ bioremediation, and dissolved Fe(II), Mn(II) and CH₄ were detected (Table 9). The availability of oxidants probably still limited the total rate of biodegradation in the source area during the final period of engineered in situ bioremediation. However, the total flux of dissolved petroleum hydrocarbons decreased from 5 mol/day at the beginning to 0.2 mol/day at the end of the study (Hunkeler *et al.*, 2002).

Which corroborate with Scow and Hicks research thus Kao *et al*, The biodegradation is naturally enhanced by providing nutrients, electron acceptors and microorganisms degrading aromatic hydrocarbons (Scow and Hicks, 2005). Kao and Prosser have adopted a mass flux approach to calculate contaminant mass reduction and field-scale decay rate at a gasoline spill site. The mass flux calculation shows that up to 87% of the dissolved total benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, and xylene (BTEX) isomers removal was observed via natural attenuation at this site.

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Table.9. Rate of supply (F) and rates of consumption (ΔF) of species involved in microbial processes in the subsurface (Hunkeler *et al.*, 2002).

Compounds Years	O ₂		NO ₃ ⁻		Mn(II)	Fe(II)	SO ₄ ²⁻		CH ₄	PHC
	F	ΔF	F	ΔF	ΔF	ΔF	F	ΔF	ΔF	ΔF
1993	32	-26	89	-80	1.0	5.6	17	-5.6	19	0.5
1994	17	-15	24	-21	0.8	8.1	12	-9.2	19	-
1995	16	11	21	-10	0.1	2.4	10	-2.6	7.8	0.2
1996	21	-14	22	-7	0.4	3.5	10	-1.5	7.8	0.2
1997	20	-13	22	-7	0.3	3.9	10	-2.2	5.8	-

All rates are in mol/day. - : not determined. O₂: oxygen. NO₃⁻: Nitrate. Mn : Manganese.
 Fe(II): ferrous. SO₄²⁻: Sulfate. PHC: Petroleum Hydrocarbons.

Results reveal that natural biodegradation was the major cause of the BTEX mass reduction among the natural attenuation processes, and approximately 88% of the BTEX removal was due to the natural biodegradation process. The calculated total BTEX first-order attenuation and biodegradation rates were 0.036 and 0.025% per day, respectively. The results reveal that natural biodegradation was the main cause of mass reduction of BTEX in natural attenuation processes, and that about 88% of BTEX removal was due to the natural biodegradation process. The first-order attenuation and biodegradation rates calculated for the total BTEX were 0.036 and 0.025% per day, respectively (Kao and Prosser, 2001).

In this study, the degradation *in vitro* of benzene and toluene using ubiquitous strains under ordinary conditions was found to be more than effective. Indeed, the added benzene and toluene was completely eliminated by all our strains after less than 30 days with the appearance of a single compound in our water, which is cyclohexane. It is a hydrogenation, with different concentrations, which can be explained by the fact that each of our bacteria degrades not only benzene or toluene but also derivatives derived from benzene. Except that the research of Widdel and Rabus, when toluene is degraded by microorganisms it converts to carbon dioxide and water. By degrading toluene, the growth of microorganisms and faster than during the degradation of other aromatic hydrocarbons (Widdel and Rabus, 2001).

While knowing that hydrogenation of benzene can only be carried out under conditions specific of temperature, pressure and particular asset catalyst. In this study, benzene is completely converted to cyclohexane under normal conditions, it is also noted that the concentration of cyclohexane decreases without the formation of other toxic secondary products.

However according to Jufeng et al, the concentration of a mixture of monoaromatic hydrocarbons in a medium plays an important role in the rapidity of biodegradation. With a concentration of about 30 mg / kg of a mixture of monaromatic hydrocarbons all these are biodegraded in about twenty days. However, the more the concentration of a mixture increases, the more the biodegradation of benzene is slow. On the other hand, that of toluene remains fast. With a concentration of 300mg / kg practically 100% of the toluene is degraded in 50 days while only 31% of the benzene will be (Jufeng *et al.*, 2007). In our essay, after 4 weeks the toluene is completely consumed and the cyclohexane appears as a secondary product except that comparing with the results of the degradation of the benzene we notice quickly that the concentration levels in the waters polluted with the benzene are much higher than those of the waters polluted with toluene, that is to say the degradation of toluene by our strains was faster than with benzene. For example, the S1663 (*Enterococcus faecalis*) strain after 4 weeks, the level of cyclohexane from benzene is 0.0964 $\mu\text{g} / \mu\text{l}$, while the one from toluene is 0.0183 $\mu\text{g} / \mu\text{l}$. Indeed, after 60 days, the two strains S1687 (*Serratia marcescens*) and S1671 (*Acinetobacter baumannii*) have concentrations of cyclohexane from benzene: 0.0746 $\mu\text{g} / \mu\text{l}$ and 0.0705 $\mu\text{g} / \mu\text{l}$ respectively, however they have completely consumed toluene and these derivatives after the same period.

Indeed, strains S1670 (*Acinetobacter baumannii*), S1671 (*Acinetobacter baumannii*) and S1620 (*Klebsiella pneumoniae*) degrade benzene faster than cyclohexane according to the results obtained. After 4weeks, cyclohexane concentrations were 0.0475 $\mu\text{g} / \mu\text{l}$, 0.0727 $\mu\text{g} / \mu\text{l}$ and 0.0599 $\mu\text{g} / \mu\text{l}$ respectively. Whereas after 63 days the concentrations decreased slightly as follows 0.0457 $\mu\text{g} / \mu\text{l}$, 0.0705 $\mu\text{g} / \mu\text{l}$ and 0.0483 $\mu\text{g} / \mu\text{l}$.

According to researches of Reinhard, the rates of benzene's biodegradation through bacteria were negligible (Reinhard *et al.*, 2005), while the experiments of Anderson and Lovley have proved the degradation of benzene within 25 a 35 days (Anderson and Lovley, 2000).

The S1663 strain (*Enterococcus faecalis*) degrades benzene much less rapidly than cyclohexane, as shown by concentrations 0.0964 $\mu\text{g} / \mu\text{l}$ (after 30 days) and 0.0446 $\mu\text{g} / \mu\text{l}$ (after 63 days).

The same behavior is observed with S05 (*Citrobacter freundii*) and S476 (*Citrobacter youngae*), which had found difficulties to degrade benzene, but degrade more readily cyclohexane. Grbic-Gralic and Vogel found that total benzene's biodegradation occurs only in the absence of any other carbon substrate, and that when other monoaromatic hydrocarbons are present with higher amounts than benzene, degradation of benzene did not happen. This shows that bacteria degrade benzene only as a

last resort, because benzene is the most resistant pollutant in almost all field studies, as a carcinogen and therefore the most toxic (Grbic-Gralic and Vogel,1987). For the remains of the bacteria of this study, S02 (*Klebsiella oxytoca*), S1687 (*Serratia marcescens*), S1664 (*Klebsiella pneumonia*) and S1850 (*Pseudomonas aeruginosa*) they proceed to a proportionately considerable elimination of cyclohexane, after having completely eliminated the benzene.

Conclusion and perspectives

This study allowed us to know that the water resources are actually exposed to several types of pollution and mainly by the Skikda RA1K-Algeria oil industry which rejects a lot of substances that will pollute our rivers and our aquifers, and depending on the nature or the importance of the pollution, different treatment processes can be implemented for the purification of rejected water that meets the discharge standards (physicochemical and biological processes ...).

Our work permits us to evaluate the aerobic degradation performance of benzene and toluene through 10 ubiquitous bacteria in the aqueous phase. This indicates the reliability of biological treatment without resorting to other types of processes (physicochemical techniques). The big challenge is the use of our bacteria on a large scale, to treat high concentrations of industrial aromatic hydrocarbons, which can be accomplished by inoculating our strains in immobilized Bioreactors containing concentrations more and more high levels of aromatics hydrocarbons, allowing them to adapt and tolerate high concentrations (Shim 1997, Shim and Yang 1999). In addition, co-cultivation would undoubtedly have very promising applications in the treatment of water contaminated by industrial discharges, in order to improve the productivity of purification plants and to contain environmental damage.

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